

Unit Commitment of Integrated Electricity and Heat System with Bi-directional Variable Mass Flow - Online Appendix

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NOMENCLATURE

A. Indices and Sets

1) General Integrated System:

\mathcal{T} Set of indices of scheduling time periods.

2) Electrical Power System:

\mathcal{I}^{TU} Set of indices of TU units.
 \mathcal{I}^{WF} Set of indices of wind farms.
 \mathcal{I}^{BUS} Set of indices of buses in the electrical power system.

$\mathcal{S}_i^{\text{BUS}}$ Set of indices of buses connecting to bus i .
 $\mathcal{S}_i^{\text{TU}}$ Set of indices of thermal units connecting to bus i .

$\mathcal{S}_i^{\text{WF}}$ Set of indices of wind farms connecting to bus i .

$\mathcal{S}_i^{\text{CHP}}$ Set of indices of CHP units connecting to bus i .

$\mathcal{S}_i^{\text{HP}}$ Set of indices of heat pumps connecting to bus i .

$\mathcal{S}_i^{\text{HS}}$ Set of indices of heat source stations connecting to bus i .

3) District Heating System:

\mathcal{I}^{CHP} Set of indices of combined heat-and-power (CHP) units.

\mathcal{I}^{HP} Set of indices of heat pump (HP) units.

\mathcal{I}^{HS} Set of indices of heat source station.

$\mathcal{S}_n^{\text{PF}}$ Set of indices of pipelines connecting from node n .

$\mathcal{S}_n^{\text{PT}}$ Set of indices of pipelines connecting to node n .

$\mathcal{S}_n^{\text{HS}}$ Set of indices of heat stations connecting at node n .

$\mathcal{S}_n^{\text{HES}}$ Set of indices of heat exchange stations connecting at node n .

B. Input Parameters and Functions

1) General Integrated System:

$c_g^{\text{SU}}/c_g^{\text{SD}}$ Startup/Shutdown cost of unit g .

$\alpha_{i,g}$ i th cost coefficient of unit g .

2) Electrical Power System:

$C_g^{\text{TU}}(\cdot)$ Operation cost function of TU unit g .
 $C_g^{\text{WF}}(\cdot)$ Penalty cost of wind power spillage of wind farm g .

$f_g^{\text{TU}}(\cdot)$ Operating cost function of TU unit g .
 $d_{i,t}^{\text{LOAD}}$ Electrical power load at bus i during time period t .

$\underline{p}_g, \bar{p}_g$ Minimum/Maximum electrical power output of generation unit g .

$\overline{su}_g/\overline{sd}_g$ Startup/Shutdown ramping capability of generation unit g during one single time period.

$\overline{ru}_g/\overline{rd}_g$ Upward/downward ramping capability of generation unit g during one single time period.

$RU_{\text{sys},t}/RD_{\text{sys},t}$ System wide upward/downward spinning reserve capacity requirement during time period t .

mu_g/md_g Minimum numbers of uptime/downtime time periods of generation unit t .

$X_{i,t}$ Reactance of transmission line connection bus i and bus j .

$\bar{f}_{i,j}$ Transmission Capacity of transmission line connection bus i and bus j .

3) District Heating System:

$C_g^{\text{CHP}}(\cdot)$ Operation cost function of CHP unit g .
 $f_g^{\text{CHP}}(\cdot)$ Operating cost function of CHP unit g .

$(\cdot)^+$ Maximum value of variable and zero.
 $(\cdot)^-$ Minimum value of variable and zero.

$\mu_b^{\text{PS}}/\mu_b^{\text{PR}}$ Coefficient of pressure loss of pipeline b in the supply/return network.

$\underline{m}_b^{\text{PS}}/\underline{m}_b^{\text{PR}}$ Lower limit of mass flow rate of pipeline b in the supply/return network.

$\overline{m}_b^{\text{PS}}/\overline{m}_b^{\text{PR}}$ Upper limit of mass flow rate of pipeline b in the supply/return network.

ρ Density of water.

$A_b^{\text{PS}}/A_b^{\text{PR}}$ Cross-sectional area of pipeline b in the supply/return network.

c	Specific heat capacity of water.
τ_t^{AMB}	Ambient temperature during time period t .
$R_b^{\text{PS}}/R_b^{\text{PR}}$	Thermal resistance of pipeline b in the supply/return network.
NK_i	Number of extreme points in the feasible operating region of heat station unit i .
P_i^k	Electric output corresponding to the k th extreme point in the feasible operating region of CHP unit i .
H_i^k	Heat output corresponding to the k th extreme point in the feasible operating region of CHP unit i .
$\underline{\tau}_n^{\text{NS}}/\overline{\tau}_n^{\text{NS}}$	Minimum/maximum temperature at node n in the supply network.
$\underline{\tau}_n^{\text{NR}}/\overline{\tau}_n^{\text{NR}}$	Minimum/maximum temperature at node n in the return network.
$\underline{d}_j^{\text{PUMP}}/\overline{d}_j^{\text{PUMP}}$	Lower/upper limit of electric power consumption of water pump in heat source station j
pr_l^{HES}	Minimum heat load pressure of heat exchange station l .
C_l^{BUI}	Thermal capacity of aggregated building connecting to heat exchange station l .
R_l^{BUI}	Thermal resistance of aggregated building connecting to heat exchange station l .
$\underline{\tau}_l^{\text{ROOM}}/\overline{\tau}_l^{\text{ROOM}}$	Lower/upper limit of room temperature of aggregated building connected to heat exchange station l to ensure the thermal comfort.

C. Decision Variables

1) General Integrated System:

$us_{g,t}$	Unit state of unit g during time period t , 1 if the unit is on and 0 otherwise.
$su_{g,t}$	Startup state of unit g during time period t , 1 if the unit is started up and 0 otherwise.
$sd_{g,t}$	Shutdown state of unit g during time period t , 1 if the unit is started up and 0 otherwise.

2) Electrical Power System:

$p_{g,t}$	Electric output of generation unit g during period t .
$ru_{g,t}/rd_{g,t}$	Upward/downward spinning reserve capacity of thermal unit g during time period t .
$\theta_{i,t}$	Phase angle of bus i voltage during time period t .

3) District Heating System:

$m_{b,t}^{\text{PS}}/m_{b,t}^{\text{PR}}$	Mass flow rate of pipeline b during time period t in the supply/return network.
$m_{b,t}^{\text{PS},+}/m_{b,t}^{\text{PR},+}$	First slack variables in the supply/return network.
$m_{b,t}^{\text{PS},-}/m_{b,t}^{\text{PR},-}$	Second slack variables in the supply/return network.
$pr_{n,t}^{\text{NS}}/pr_{n,t}^{\text{NR}}$	Pressure head at node n during time period t in the supply/return network.
$\tau_{b,t,x}^{\text{PS}}/\tau_{b,t,x}^{\text{PR}}$	Temperature of control volume in pipeline b in the supply/return network with the

$\tau_{n,t}^{\text{NS}}/\tau_{n,t}^{\text{NR}}$	Mixed temperature at node n in the supply/return network during time period t .
$m_{j,t}^{\text{HS}}$	Mass flow of heat station l during period t .
$m_{l,t}^{\text{HES}}$	Mass flow of heat exchange station j during period t .
$p_{i,t}$	Electric output of generation unit i during period t .
$h_{i,t}$	Heat output of generation unit i during period t .
$\alpha_{i,t}^k$	Variable for representing the operating point of CHP unit i corresponding to the k th extreme point in the feasible operating region at period t .
$d_{j,t}^{\text{PUMP}}$	Electric power consumption of water pump in heat source station j during time period t
$h_{l,t}^{\text{HES}}$	Heat load of heat exchange station l during time period t .
$\tau_{l,t}^{\text{ROOM}}$	Room temperature in the aggregated building during time period t connected to heat exchange station l .

I. INTRODUCTION

It is an online appendix document for "Unit Commitment of Integrated Electricity and Heat System with Bi-directional Variable Mass Flow". In order to introduce the unit commitment problem of integrated electricity and heat system (IEHS) in a better way, a more detailed and easy-reading description is given in the next section. More specifically, the objective function is described in II-A, the constraints from district heating system and electrical power system are described in II-B and II-C respectively. Besides, some additional formula derivation process is added in order to make it more complete.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

A. Objective Function

The objective of the day-ahead unit commitment is to minimize the total operation cost of the integrated energy system

$$\min \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{g \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{TU}}} C_{g,t}^{\text{TU}} + \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{g \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{CHP}}} C_{g,t}^{\text{CHP}} + \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{g \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{WF}}} C_{g,t}^{\text{WF}} \quad (1)$$

the operation cost of TU and CHP unit g is defined as follows

$$C_{g,t} = f_{g,t} + c_g^{\text{SU}} su_{g,t} + c_g^{\text{SD}} sd_{g,t}, \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{TU}} \cup \mathcal{I}^{\text{CHP}}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (2)$$

$$f_g = \sum_{k=1}^{NK_g} \alpha_{g,t,k} C_{g,t}, \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{TU}} \cup \mathcal{I}^{\text{CHP}}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (3)$$

the penalty cost of wind farm g is proportional to the wind power curtailment

$$C_{g,t} = \sigma_g (\bar{p}_{g,t} - p_{g,t}), \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{WF}}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (4)$$

B. Constraints of District Heating System

The proposed district heating system model is based on the thermodynamics of heat flow.

1) Constraints of Heat Source Station:

Heat production units in heat stations could include combined heat and power production unit (CHP), heat pump (HP), electric boiler (EB), etc. The relationship of electric and heat power could be modeled as [1]

$$p_{g,t} = \sum_{k=1}^{NK_g} \alpha_{g,t,k} P_{g,k}, \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{TU}} \cup \mathcal{I}^{\text{CHP}}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (5)$$

$$h_{g,t} = \sum_{k=1}^{NK_g} \alpha_{g,t,k} H_{g,k}, \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{CHP}}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{NK_g} \alpha_{g,t,k} = us_{g,t}, 0 \leq \alpha_{g,t,k} \leq 1, \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{TU}} \cup \mathcal{I}^{\text{CHP}}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (7)$$

The heat output from heat station is used to heat the water flow through the connected node

$$h_{j,t} = cm_{j,t}^{\text{HS}}(\tau_{n,t}^{\text{NS}} - \tau_{n,t}^{\text{NR}}), \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{CHP}}, j \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{HS}}, \quad (8)$$

$$n = \text{Nd}_j^{\text{HS}}, t \in \mathcal{T}$$

The supply temperature of water flow should be kept within a threshold to ensure the supply water quality

$$\underline{\tau}_n^{\text{NS}} \leq \tau_{n,t}^{\text{NS}} \leq \bar{\tau}_n^{\text{NS}}, \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{HS}}, n = \text{Nd}_j^{\text{HS}}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (9)$$

Water pump is usually installed at the heat station to pump the water from the return network into the supply network, the electric power consumed is proportional to the pressure difference and the mass flow rate

$$d_{j,t}^{\text{WP}} = \frac{m_{j,t}^{\text{HS}}(pr_{n,t}^{\text{NS}} - pr_{n,t}^{\text{NR}})}{\eta_j^{\text{WP}} \cdot \rho}, \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{HS}}, n = \text{Nd}_j^{\text{HS}}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (10)$$

$$\underline{d}_j^{\text{WP}} \leq d_{j,t}^{\text{WP}} \leq \bar{d}_j^{\text{WP}}, \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{HS}}, n = \text{Nd}_j^{\text{HS}}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (11)$$

2) Constraints of Heat transmission pipeline:

Firstly, the water flow in a heat transmission pipeline is driven by the pressure difference between the two terminals of the pipeline. Take a pipe b with the two terminals denoted as $n1$ and $n2$ in the supply network as an example, it is defined that $m_{b,t}^{\text{PS}} > 0$ if it flows from node $n1$ to node $n2$, $m_{b,t}^{\text{PS}} < 0$ if it flows from node $n2$ to $n1$, and $m_{b,t}^{\text{PS}} = 0$ if water in the pipeline doesn't flow. According to the Darcy-Weisbach equation [2], the pressure loss in the pipeline is proportional to the square of mass flow rate

$$pr_{n1,t}^{\text{NS}} - pr_{n2,t}^{\text{NS}} = \mu_b^{\text{PS}} m_{b,t}^{\text{PS}} |m_{b,t}^{\text{PS}}|, \quad \forall b \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{PIPE}}, t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (12)$$

$$n1 = \text{Nd}_b^{\text{PF}}, n2 = \text{Nd}_b^{\text{PT}}$$

$$pr_{n2,t}^{\text{NR}} - pr_{n1,t}^{\text{NR}} = \mu_b^{\text{PR}} m_{b,t}^{\text{PR}} |m_{b,t}^{\text{PR}}|, \quad \forall b \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{PIPE}}, t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (13)$$

$$n1 = \text{Nd}_b^{\text{PF}}, n2 = \text{Nd}_b^{\text{PT}}$$

Besides, the mass flow rate in pipeline should be kept within the technical limit

$$-\bar{m}_b^{\text{PS}} \leq m_{b,t}^{\text{PS}} \leq \bar{m}_b^{\text{PS}}, \quad \forall b \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{PIPE}}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (14)$$

$$-\bar{m}_b^{\text{PR}} \leq m_{b,t}^{\text{PR}} \leq \bar{m}_b^{\text{PR}}, \quad \forall b \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{PIPE}}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (15)$$

In order to eliminate the absolute value operation, (12) is formulated as (16)-(18) and (13) is formulated as (19)-(21) through introducing two non-negative slack variables and using complementary slackness condition [3], [4].

$$m_{b,t}^{\text{PS}} = m_{b,t}^{\text{PS,+}} - m_{b,t}^{\text{PS,-}}, \quad \forall b \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{PIPE}}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (16)$$

$$pr_{n1,t}^{\text{NS}} - pr_{n2,t}^{\text{NS}} = \mu_b^{\text{PS}} \left[\left(m_{b,t}^{\text{PS,+}} \right)^2 - \left(m_{b,t}^{\text{PS,-}} \right)^2 \right], \quad (17)$$

$$\forall b \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{PIPE}}, t \in \mathcal{T}, n1 = \text{Nd}_b^{\text{PF}}, n2 = \text{Nd}_b^{\text{PT}}$$

$$m_{b,t}^{\text{PS,+}} m_{b,t}^{\text{PS,-}} = 0, \quad 0 \leq m_{b,t}^{\text{PS,+}} \leq \bar{m}_b^{\text{PS}}, \quad (18)$$

$$0 \leq m_{b,t}^{\text{PS,-}} \leq \bar{m}_b^{\text{PS}}, \quad \forall b \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{PIPE}}, t \in \mathcal{T}$$

$$m_{b,t}^{\text{PR}} = m_{b,t}^{\text{PR,+}} - m_{b,t}^{\text{PR,-}}, \quad \forall b \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{PIPE}}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (19)$$

$$pr_{n2,t}^{\text{NR}} - pr_{n1,t}^{\text{NR}} = \mu_b^{\text{PR}} \left[\left(m_{b,t}^{\text{PR,+}} \right)^2 - \left(m_{b,t}^{\text{PR,-}} \right)^2 \right], \quad (20)$$

$$\forall b \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{PIPE}}, t \in \mathcal{T}, n1 = \text{Nd}_b^{\text{PF}}, n2 = \text{Nd}_b^{\text{PT}}$$

$$m_{b,t}^{\text{PR,+}} m_{b,t}^{\text{PR,-}} = 0, \quad 0 \leq m_{b,t}^{\text{PR,+}} \leq \bar{m}_b^{\text{PR}}, \quad (21)$$

$$0 \leq m_{b,t}^{\text{PR,-}} \leq \bar{m}_b^{\text{PR}}, \quad \forall b \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{PIPE}}, t \in \mathcal{T}$$

The temperature distribution along a heat transmission pipeline is governed by the partial differential equation [5], [6]

$$\rho A c \frac{\partial \tau}{\partial t} + m c \frac{\partial \tau}{\partial x} - \frac{m}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} - \left| \frac{m}{\rho A} \right|^3 \frac{\rho f_D S}{2} - k A \frac{\partial^2 \tau}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\tau - \tau^{\text{AMB}}}{R} = 0 \quad (22)$$

There are 6 terms in (22), the 1st term and 2nd term describe the time derivative and spatial derivative of temperature distribution respectively, the 3rd term describes the spatial derivative of pressure, the 4th term describes the wall friction dissipation, the 5th term describes the axial heat diffusion, and the 6th term describes the heat loss.

According to the general assumptions of the modelling of district heating system [7], the impacts of 3rd - 5th terms could be ignored, hence the original partial differential equation (22) would be simplified as

$$\rho A_b^{\text{PS}} c \frac{\partial \tau}{\partial t} + m_{b,t}^{\text{PS}} c \frac{\partial \tau}{\partial x} + \frac{\tau - \tau_t^{\text{AMB}}}{R_b^{\text{PS}}} = 0, \quad \forall b \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{PIPE}}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (23)$$

An implicit upwind scheme used in [8] is adopted to discrete the partial differential equation

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \rho A_b^{\text{PS}} c \frac{\tau_{b,t,x}^{\text{PS}} - \tau_{b,t-1,x}^{\text{PS}}}{\Delta t} + m_{b,t}^{\text{PS}} c \frac{\tau_{b,t,x}^{\text{PS}} - \tau_{b,t,x-1}^{\text{PS}}}{\Delta x} \\ \quad + \frac{\tau_{b,t,x}^{\text{PS}} - \tau_t^{\text{AMB}}}{R_b^{\text{PS}}} = 0 \quad m_{b,t}^{\text{PS}} > 0, \\ \rho A_b^{\text{PS}} c \frac{\tau_{b,t,x}^{\text{PS}} - \tau_{b,t-1,x}^{\text{PS}}}{\Delta t} + m_{b,t}^{\text{PS}} c \frac{\tau_{b,t,x+1}^{\text{PS}} - \tau_{b,t,x}^{\text{PS}}}{\Delta x} \\ \quad + \frac{\tau_{b,t,x}^{\text{PS}} - \tau_t^{\text{AMB}}}{R_b^{\text{PS}}} = 0 \quad m_{b,t}^{\text{PS}} < 0, \\ \forall b \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{PIPE}}, t \in \mathcal{T}, x \in \{1, 2, \dots, N_b\} \end{array} \right. \quad (24)$$

For simplicity, (24) could be written in a compact form with (25) and (26)

$$\rho A_b^{\text{PS}} c \frac{\tau_{b,t,x}^{\text{PS}} - \tau_{b,t-1,x}^{\text{PS}}}{\Delta t} + (m_{b,t}^{\text{PS}})^+ c \frac{\tau_{b,t,x}^{\text{PS}} - \tau_{b,t,x-1}^{\text{PS}}}{\Delta x} + (m_{b,t}^{\text{PS}})^- c \frac{\tau_{b,t,x+1}^{\text{PS}} - \tau_{b,t,x}^{\text{PS}}}{\Delta x} + \frac{\tau_{b,t,x}^{\text{PS}} - \tau_t^{\text{AMB}}}{R_b^{\text{PS}}} = 0, \quad (25)$$

$$\forall b \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{PIPE}}, t \in \mathcal{T}, x \in \{1, 2, \dots, N_b\}$$

$$(m_{b,t}^{\text{PS}})^+ = \max(m_{b,t}^{\text{PS}}, 0), \quad (m_{b,t}^{\text{PS}})^- = \min(m_{b,t}^{\text{PS}}, 0),$$

$$\forall b \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{PIPE}}, t \in \mathcal{T}$$

(26)

By using the two introduced non-negative slack variables, (25)-(26) is formulated as (27) to eliminate the maximum/minimum value operations

$$\rho A_b^{\text{PS}} c \frac{\tau_{b,t,x}^{\text{PS}} - \tau_{b,t-1,x}^{\text{PS}}}{\Delta t} + m_{b,t}^{\text{PS},+} c \frac{\tau_{b,t,x}^{\text{PS}} - \tau_{b,t,x-1}^{\text{PS}}}{\Delta x} - m_{b,t}^{\text{PS},-} c \frac{\tau_{b,t,x+1}^{\text{PS}} - \tau_{b,t,x}^{\text{PS}}}{\Delta x} + \frac{\tau_{b,t,x}^{\text{PS}} - \tau_t^{\text{AMB}}}{R_b^{\text{PS}}} = 0, \quad (27)$$

$$\forall b \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{PIPE}}, t \in \mathcal{T}, x \in \{1, 2, \dots, N_b\}$$

Similarly, the temperature distribution along the return pipeline could be written as

$$\rho A_b^{\text{PR}} c \frac{\tau_{b,t,x}^{\text{PR}} - \tau_{b,t-1,x}^{\text{PR}}}{\Delta t} - m_{b,t}^{\text{PR},+} c \frac{\tau_{b,t,x+1}^{\text{PR}} - \tau_{b,t,x}^{\text{PR}}}{\Delta x} + m_{b,t}^{\text{PR},-} c \frac{\tau_{b,t,x}^{\text{PR}} - \tau_{b,t,x-1}^{\text{PR}}}{\Delta x} + \frac{\tau_{b,t,x}^{\text{PR}} - \tau_t^{\text{AMB}}}{R_b^{\text{PR}}} = 0, \quad (28)$$

$$\forall b \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{PIPE}}, t \in \mathcal{T}, x \in \{1, 2, \dots, N_b\}$$

3) Constraints of Connecting Nodes:

For a general connecting node in the district heating system, the total water flow into the node equals to the total water flow from the node

$$\sum_{b \in \mathcal{S}_n^{\text{PT}}} m_{b,t}^{\text{PS}} + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{S}_n^{\text{HS}}} m_{j,t}^{\text{HS}} = \sum_{b \in \mathcal{S}_n^{\text{PF}}} m_{b,t}^{\text{PS}} + \sum_{l \in \mathcal{S}_n^{\text{HES}}} m_{l,t}^{\text{HES}}, \quad (29)$$

$$\forall n \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{NODE}}, t \in \mathcal{T}$$

$$\sum_{b \in \mathcal{S}_n^{\text{PT}}} m_{b,t}^{\text{PR}} + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{S}_n^{\text{HS}}} m_{j,t}^{\text{HS}} = \sum_{b \in \mathcal{S}_n^{\text{PF}}} m_{b,t}^{\text{PR}} + \sum_{l \in \mathcal{S}_n^{\text{HES}}} m_{l,t}^{\text{HES}}, \quad (30)$$

$$\forall n \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{NODE}}, t \in \mathcal{T}$$

For the mixed temperature of the node, the energy conservation for the node temperature is

$$\sum_{b \in \mathcal{S}_n^{\text{PT}}} \tau_{b,t,N_b}^{\text{PS}} (m_{b,t}^{\text{PS}})^+ - \sum_{b \in \mathcal{S}_n^{\text{PF}}} \tau_{b,t,1}^{\text{PS}} (m_{b,t}^{\text{PS}})^- + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{S}_n^{\text{HS}}} \tau_{j,t}^{\text{HS}} m_{j,t}^{\text{HS}} = \tau_{t,n}^{\text{NS}} \left[\sum_{b \in \mathcal{S}_n^{\text{PT}}} (m_{b,t}^{\text{PS}})^+ - \sum_{b \in \mathcal{S}_n^{\text{PF}}} (m_{b,t}^{\text{PS}})^- + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{S}_n^{\text{HS}}} m_{j,t}^{\text{HS}} \right], \quad (31)$$

$$\forall n \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{NODE}}, t \in \mathcal{T}$$

By using the two introduced non-negative slack variables, (31) is formulated as (32) to eliminate the maximum/minimum value operation

$$\sum_{b \in \mathcal{S}_n^{\text{PT}}} \tau_{b,t,N_b}^{\text{PS}} m_{b,t}^{\text{PS},+} + \sum_{b \in \mathcal{S}_n^{\text{PF}}} \tau_{b,t,1}^{\text{PS}} m_{b,t}^{\text{PS},-} + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{S}_n^{\text{HS}}} \tau_{j,t}^{\text{HS}} m_{j,t}^{\text{HS}} = \tau_{t,n}^{\text{NS}} \left(\sum_{b \in \mathcal{S}_n^{\text{PT}}} m_{b,t}^{\text{PS},+} + \sum_{b \in \mathcal{S}_n^{\text{PF}}} m_{b,t}^{\text{PS},-} + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{S}_n^{\text{HS}}} m_{j,t}^{\text{HS}} \right), \quad (32)$$

$$\forall n \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{NODE}}, t \in \mathcal{T}$$

Similarly, the temperature mix equation in the return node could be written as

$$\sum_{b \in \mathcal{S}_n^{\text{PT}}} \tau_{b,t,N_b}^{\text{PR}} m_{b,t}^{\text{PR},-} + \sum_{b \in \mathcal{S}_n^{\text{PF}}} \tau_{b,t,1}^{\text{PR}} m_{b,t}^{\text{PR},+} + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{S}_n^{\text{HES}}} \tau_{j,t}^{\text{HES}} m_{j,t}^{\text{HES}} = \tau_{t,n}^{\text{NR}} \left(\sum_{b \in \mathcal{S}_n^{\text{PT}}} m_{b,t}^{\text{PR},-} + \sum_{b \in \mathcal{S}_n^{\text{PF}}} m_{b,t}^{\text{PR},+} + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{S}_n^{\text{HES}}} m_{j,t}^{\text{HES}} \right), \quad (33)$$

$$\forall n \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{NODE}}, t \in \mathcal{T}$$

The temperature of mass flowing into a pipeline is equal to the mixed temperature of the corresponding node, which also served as the pipeline boundary condition

$$\tau_{b,t,1}^{\text{PS}} (m_{b,t}^{\text{PS}})^+ + \tau_{b,t,N_b}^{\text{PS}} (m_{b,t}^{\text{PS}})^- = \tau_{t,n1}^{\text{NS}} (m_{b,t}^{\text{PS}})^+ + \tau_{t,n2}^{\text{NS}} (m_{b,t}^{\text{PS}})^-, \quad \forall b \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{PIPE}}, t \in \mathcal{T}, n1 = \text{Nd}_b^{\text{PF}}, n2 = \text{Nd}_b^{\text{PT}} \quad (34)$$

$$\tau_{b,t,N_b}^{\text{PR}} (m_{b,t}^{\text{PR}})^+ + \tau_{b,t,1}^{\text{PR}} (m_{b,t}^{\text{PR}})^- = \tau_{t,n1}^{\text{NR}} (m_{b,t}^{\text{PR}})^+ + \tau_{t,n2}^{\text{NR}} (m_{b,t}^{\text{PR}})^-, \quad \forall b \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{PIPE}}, t \in \mathcal{T}, n1 = \text{Nd}_b^{\text{PF}}, n2 = \text{Nd}_b^{\text{PT}} \quad (35)$$

By using the two introduced non-negative slack variables, (34) is formulated as (36) and (35) is formulated as (37) to eliminate the maximum/minimum value operation

$$\tau_{b,t,1}^{\text{PS}} m_{b,t}^{\text{PS},+} - \tau_{b,t,N_b}^{\text{PS}} m_{b,t}^{\text{PS},-} = \tau_{t,n1}^{\text{NS}} m_{b,t}^{\text{PS},+} - \tau_{t,n2}^{\text{NS}} m_{b,t}^{\text{PS},-}, \quad \forall b \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{PIPE}}, t \in \mathcal{T}, n1 = \text{Nd}_b^{\text{PF}}, n2 = \text{Nd}_b^{\text{PT}} \quad (36)$$

$$\tau_{b,t,N_b}^{\text{PR}} m_{b,t}^{\text{PR},+} - \tau_{b,t,1}^{\text{PR}} m_{b,t}^{\text{PR},-} = \tau_{t,n1}^{\text{NR}} m_{b,t}^{\text{PR},+} - \tau_{t,n2}^{\text{NR}} m_{b,t}^{\text{PR},-}, \quad \forall b \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{PIPE}}, t \in \mathcal{T}, n1 = \text{Nd}_b^{\text{PF}}, n2 = \text{Nd}_b^{\text{PT}} \quad (37)$$

4) Constraints of Heat Exchange Station:

Heat exchange stations are modeled as loads in the primary district heating system, while as sources in the secondary district heating system

$$cm_{l,t}^{\text{HES}} (\tau_{n,t}^{\text{NS}} - \tau_{n,t}^{\text{NR}}) = h_{l,t}^{\text{HES}}, \quad \forall l \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{HES}}, n = \text{Nd}_l^{\text{HES}}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (38)$$

$$pr_{n,t}^{\text{NS}} - pr_{n,t}^{\text{NR}} \geq pr_l^{\text{HES}}, \quad \forall l \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{HES}}, n = \text{Nd}_l^{\text{HES}}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (39)$$

$$\tau_n^{\text{NR}} \leq \tau_{n,t} \leq \bar{\tau}_n^{\text{NR}}, \quad \forall n = \text{Nd}_j^{\text{HES}}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (40)$$

C. Constraints of Electrical Power System

The DC power flow is used to formulate the constraints of electrical power system [9].

1) Constraints of TU Unit Electricity Output:

The electricity output of TU unit g could be expressed as

$$p_{g,t} = \sum_{k=1}^{NK_g} \alpha_{g,t,k} P_{g,k}, \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{I}^{TU}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (41)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{NK_g} \alpha_{g,t,k} = u_{s_{g,t}}, \quad 0 \leq \alpha_{g,t,k} \leq 1, \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{I}^{TU}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (42)$$

2) Constraints of Power Balance:

The total electrical power generation and loads should be balanced at each time period

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{g \in \mathcal{I}^{TU}} p_{g,t} + \sum_{g \in \mathcal{I}^{CHP}} p_{g,t} + \sum_{g \in \mathcal{I}^{WF}} p_{g,t} \\ = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}^B} D_{i,t}^{EL} + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{I}^{HS}} d_{j,t}^{WP}, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \end{aligned} \quad (43)$$

3) Constraints of Spinning Reserve:

TU units should provide the required level of spinning reserve capacity

$$p_{g,t} + ru_{g,t} \leq \bar{p}_g u_{s_{g,t}} - (\bar{p}_g - \bar{s}u_g) su_{g,t}, \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{I}^{TU}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (44)$$

$$p_{g,t} + ru_{g,t} \leq \bar{p}_g u_{s_{g,t}} - (\bar{p}_g - \bar{s}d_g) su_{g,t+1}, \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{I}^{TU}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (45)$$

$$p_{g,t} - rd_{g,t} \geq \underline{p}_g u_{s_{g,t}}, \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{I}^{TU}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (46)$$

$$\sum_{g \in \mathcal{I}^{TU}} ru_{g,t} \geq RU_t^{SYS}, \quad \sum_{g \in \mathcal{I}^{TU}} rd_{g,t} \geq RD_t^{SYS}, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (47)$$

4) Constraints of Ramping Capability:

The incremental change in the generation dispatch of a TU between two adjacent time is restricted by its ramping capability

$$-\bar{r}d_g \leq p_{g,t} - p_{g,t-1} \leq \bar{r}u_g, \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{I}^{TU} \cup \mathcal{I}^{CHP}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (48)$$

5) Constraints of Wind Farm Generation:

Electrical power output of wind farm at time period is limited by its available wind power

$$0 \leq p_{g,t} \leq \bar{p}_{g,t}, \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{I}^{WF}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (49)$$

6) Constraints of Unit Status Logic:

The unit states, startup variables, and shutdown variables should satisfied the logic constraints

$$u_{s_{g,t}} - u_{s_{g,t-1}} = su_{g,t} - sd_{g,t}, \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{I}^{TU} \cup \mathcal{I}^{CHP}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (50)$$

7) Constraints of Minimum UP/Down Time:

The operation and down hours should be larger than the minimum time limit

$$\sum_{\tau=\max\{1,t-mu_g+1\}}^t su_{g,\tau} \leq u_{s_{g,t}}, \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{I}^{TU} \cup \mathcal{I}^{CHP}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (51)$$

$$\sum_{\tau=\max\{1,t-md_g+1\}}^t sd_{g,\tau} \leq 1 - u_{s_{g,t}}, \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{I}^{TU} \cup \mathcal{I}^{CHP}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (52)$$

8) Constraints of Variable Limit:

The variables of unit should satisfied the following constraints

$$0 \leq ru_{g,t} \leq \bar{r}u_g, \quad 0 \leq rd_{g,t} \leq \bar{r}d_g, \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{I}^{TU}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (53)$$

9) Constraints of Electrical Power Transmission Line:

Electrical power flows through transmission lines should be kept within the transmission capacity

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{S}_i^{BUS}} \frac{\theta_{i,t} - \theta_{j,t}}{X_{i,j}} = \sum_{g \in \mathcal{S}_i^{TU}} p_{g,t} + \sum_{g \in \mathcal{S}_i^{CHP}} p_{g,t} + \sum_{g \in \mathcal{S}_i^{WF}} p_{g,t} \\ + \sum_{g \in \mathcal{S}_i^{HS}} d_{g,t}^{WP} - D_{i,t}^{EL}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}^{BUS}, t \in \mathcal{T} \end{aligned} \quad (54)$$

$$-\bar{f}_{(i,j)} \leq \frac{\theta_{i,t} - \theta_{j,t}}{X_{i,j}} \leq \bar{f}_{(i,j)}, \quad \forall (i,j) \in \mathcal{I}^{LINE}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (55)$$

$$\theta_{ref,t} = 0, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (56)$$

To summary, the unit commitment problem is proposed with objective function of (1), constraints (2)-(21), (27)-(33), (36)-(40) from district heating system, and constraints (41)-(56) from electrical power system. It is a mixed-integer non-linear programming (MINLP) problem, and piecewise linear approximation would be used to reformulate it into mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) problem, which is described in "Unit Commitment of Integrated Electricity and Heat System with Bi-directional Variable Mass Flow".

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